

Project Management Plan

Deliverable 6.1

Work package: **WP6**

Dissemination level: **PU**

Lead partner: **ITHACA**

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Due date: **30/04/2023**

Submission date: **28/04/2023**

The OVERWATCH project has received funding from the Horizon Europe call "HORIZON-EUSPA-2021", topic HORIZON-EUSPA-2021-SPACE-02-52, under agreement No. 101082320

Deliverable	Project Management Plan
Deliverable No.	D6.1
Work Package	6
Dissemination Level	PU
Nature ¹	R
Author(s)	Dequal L. (ITHACA)
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Date	30/05/2023
Status	Revised Version
Version	3.0
Reviewed by (if applicable)	Matos N., Arnaudo E.

Deliverable abstract	The Project Management Plan defines how the OVERWATCH project will be managed, executed and controlled.
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¹ Nature of the deliverable: **R** = Report, **P** = Prototype, **D** = Demonstrator, **O** = Other

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Document revision history

Version	Date	Modification reason	Modified by
1	13/04/2023	First issue	Luciana Dequal, Vanina Fissore
2	28/04/2023	Integration of revisions, final version	Luciana Dequal, Vanina Fissore
3	30/05/2023	Revision according to reviewers' comments	Luciana Dequal, Vanina Fissore

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3	Claudio Rossi	Reviewer	LINKS
4	Nelson Matos	Reviewer	ISQ

Abbreviations

AFM	Admin and Financial Manager
CDM	Communication and Dissemination Manager

D	Deliverable
DM	Data Manager
DoA	Description of the Action
DR	Deliverable Responsible
ESM	Privacy, Ethics and Security Manager
EUPr	EU Portal referent
GA	Grant Agreement
PMP	Project Management Plan
PO	Project Officer (EUSPA)
PC	Project Coordinator
PM	Project Manager
PMs	Person Months
QPR	Quarterly Progress Report
REVRs	Reviewers
RfC	Request for Change
SM	Stakeholder Manager
TM	Technical Coordinator
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of the Project Management Plan

The purpose of this document is to define how the project will be managed, executed and controlled. This document will describe the project plan and the management activities that must be performed to ensure a successful achievement of the project objectives, including the management procedures.

1.2. Scope

This document applies to all activities aimed to achieve the overall goal of the OVERWATCH project, by setting a common framework for the different project activities to operate efficiently, including all coordination and management actions, as well as communication and dissemination activities and other activities and strategies to maximize the impact of the project.

The intended audience of this PMP are all internal project stakeholders including all members of the project team.

This document will be reviewed and updated periodically through a series of integrated processes that extend to the closure of the project. This process will result in a PMP that is progressively elaborated by updates.

1.3. Preparation and updates

This PMP has been prepared by the PC and the AFM on the basis of the GA and the activities to be performed during the project. The PC and the AFM will ensure adherence of all project activities to the processes and procedures promoted by the PMP and will execute the efficient implementation of this plan and monitor and control its overall performance.

The PMP will be reviewed periodically by the PC and the AFM throughout OVERWATCH's life cycle. Revisions to the PMP will be submitted to the Project Team without any necessary delay.

1.4. Referred Documents

This PMP refers to the following general project documents as they have served as an input to the development of the plan.

Document Title	Version	Date
Grant Agreement nr 101082320	1.0	17/10/2022

2. OVERWATCH Project Description

2.1. Project Objectives

The OVERWATCH project aims to create a more intuitive, decentralised, informed, and precise system for several types of disasters, deployable in several phases of the disaster. The developed system will ensure a safer, more resilient, and capable response infrastructure, carrying out the crisis operation more cohesively.

Specifically, the project aims to develop an Integrated holographic crisis management map, supported by EGNSS (European Global Navigation Satellite System) and CEMS (Copernicus Emergency Management Services), to improve communication, information gathering, and coordination among disaster response teams, targeting a final TRL 7 prototype system to be validated through two demonstrations in different countries. The OVERWATCH system will be powered by both Copernicus and EGNSS data and will make extensive use of state-of-art Artificial intelligence techniques to extrapolate valuable information coupling the variety of EO (Earth Observation) data with data collected from other sources (e.g. drones). This data will be stored in a dedicated Geospatial repository within the Management backend platform, which will be directly linked with an AR (Augmented Reality) user interaction/display module, providing the users with an immersive and dynamic overview of the event.

2.2. Consortium

The Consortium of the OVERWATCH project is composed by 10 partners from 5 European countries, represented by 5 Industrial/SMEs, 4 Research & Technology Organisations and 1 Public Organisation, that together have the necessary capabilities to accomplish the established project goals.

Beneficiary no.	Acronym	Designation
1	ITH	ITHACA S.R.L.
1.1	LINKS	FONDAZIONE LINKS - LEADING INNOVATION & KNOWLEDGE FOR SOCIETY
2	ISQ	INSTITUTO DE SOLDADURA E QUALIDADE
3	CBK	CENTRUM BADAN KOSMICZNYCH POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK
4	ENG	ENGINEERING - INGEGNERIA INFORMATICA SPA
5	ROBOTTO	ROBOTTO CO APS
6	INESCTEC	INESC TEC - INSTITUTO DE ENGENHARIADE SISTEMAS E COMPUTADORES, TECNOLOGIA E CIENCIA
7	HOLO	HOLO-INDUSTRIE 4.0 SOFTWARE GMBH
8	CINAMIL	EXERCITO PORTUGUES
9	ALPHA	ALPHA CONSULTANTS S.R.L.

Table 1 – OVERWATCH Consortium

2.3. Work Breakdown Structure

In order to reach the project's goals, the development and testing activities were grouped into six Work Packages, listed here below.

WP Nr	WP name	WP leader	Start Month	End Month
1	Human-centered design	CBK	1	7
2	In-field technologies empowered by EGNSS and AI	LINKS	6	28
3	Geospatial AR Decision Support System	ENG	8	29
4	System integration, validation and fine-tuning	ISQ	7	36
5	Dissemination, communication & exploitation	ALPHA	1	36
6	Project management	ITH	1	36

Table 2 – List of WPs

2.3.1. Timing of the WPs and their components

In order to address the topic requirements, development and testing activities were grouped into six Work Packages.

WP1 Human-centered design, will define and detail end-user needs along with suitable use cases and map all technical and functional requirements for the involved technologies, which entails the strong collaboration between technical partners and domain experts, who will be part of an Advisory Group. WP2 to WP3 will be responsible for the development and integration of the several modules and technologies that will provide all the features identified in WP1, while in WP4 in-field testing, demonstration and qualification activities will be performed to test the system.

WP5 will contain all the dissemination, Communication and project results exploitation activities, while WP6 is the Project Management, which will comprise the coordination of the partners and its technical tasks as well as administrative and financial aspects of the project.

Figure 1 shows the project Pert chart, explaining the interconnections between WPs, while the project Gantt chart is provided in Figure 2, depicting the timing of the different WPs.

Figure 1: Pert chart

2.3.2.Deliverables

The deliverables to be produced in the project are 32 and they are listed here below.

Del. nr	Deliverable name	Lead Beneficiary		Due date
D1.1	End-users requirements	CINAMIL	PU	31/03/23
D1.2	Functional/Technical requirements & System architecture	ENG	PU	31/05/23
D2.1	Report on AI algorithms exploiting Copernicus EMS EO data and in-field acquisitions	CBK	SEN	28/02/25
D2.2	Report on drone mapping supported by EGNSS services	LINKS	SEN	28/02/25
D2.3	Drone development report	ROBOTTO	SEN	28/02/25
D2.4	Report on fallback communication system	INESCTEC	PU	28/02/25
D3.1	AR Geospatial holographic map	HOLO	SEN	31/05/25
D3.2	Management system and AI decision support	ENG	SEN	31/03/25
D3.3	Geospatial repository & mapper	ENG	SEN	31/03/25
D4.1	Integration & validation methodology and plan	ISQ	PU	31/07/25
D4.2	Report on integration and fine-tuning	ENG	PU	30/04/25
D4.3	Report on system demonstration, feedback workshops and training activities	CINAMIL	PU	31/10/25
D5.1	Dissemination and Communication Plan	ALPHA	PU	30/04/23
D5.2	Report on Dissemination and Communication activities	ALPHA	PU	30/04/24
D5.3	Market assessment and Business plan	ALPHA	SEN	30/04/24
D5.4	Synergies & collaboration report	CBK	PU	31/10/25
D5.5	Exploitation plan and first exploitation activities	ITH	SEN	31/10/25
D6.1	Project Management Plan and execution	ITH	PU	30/04/23
D6.2	Data management plan	ITH	PU	30/04/23
D6.3	Privacy, ethics and security report	ALPHA	PU	31/10/23
D6.4	Quarterly Report 1	ITH	SEN	31/01/23
D6.5	Quarterly Report 2	ITH	SEN	30/04/23
D6.6	Quarterly Report 3	ITH	SEN	31/07/23
D6.7	Quarterly Report 4	ITH	SEN	31/10/23
D6.8	Quarterly Report 5	ITH	SEN	31/01/24
D6.9	Quarterly Report 6	ITH	SEN	30/04/24
D6.10	Quarterly Report 7	ITH	SEN	31/07/24
D6.11	Quarterly Report 8	ITH	SEN	31/10/24
D6.12	Quarterly Report 9	ITH	SEN	31/01/25
D6.13	Quarterly Report 10	ITH	SEN	30/04/25
D6.14	Quarterly Report 11	ITH	SEN	31/07/25
D6.15	Quarterly Report 12	ITH	SEN	31/10/25

Table 3 – List of deliverables

2.3.3. Milestones

The following Milestones list has been defined in the project proposal and included in the GA. This list is used to monitor the progress of the OVERWATCH project. Deviations from this baseline will be regularly measured and reported to ensure project success.

ML #	Resp.	Title / Description	Target date
1	ITH	Kick-off meeting	30/11/23
2	ALPHA	DMP and D&C plan available	30/04/23
3	CBK	User and system requirements definition	31/03/23
4	ISQ	Architecture and technical requirements defined, first draft for integration plan	30/09/23
5	ITH	Mid-Term Review + Implementation Review (MTR)	30/04/24
6	ENG	OVERWATCH system ready for public demonstrations	28/02/25
7	CINAMIL	Demonstrations and User Feedback Workshop	31/10/25
8	ITH	Final project meeting	31/10/25

Table 4 – List of milestones

2.4. Budget

The following table presents the overall budget of the OVERWATCH project, aggregated by Partner and by cost category.

As regards subcontracting activities, here follows a brief explanation of the costs freeseen:

LINKS: € 10.000 for image labelling – a labelling campaign to fine-tune the supervised machine learning algorithms that will be trained for flood and fire mapping

ALPHA: € 34.000 for dissemination & communication

Corporate design € 6.000

Website € 10.000

printed and digital materials €10.000

videos € 8.000

No	Beneficiary	Personnel costs/€	Subcontracting costs/€	Purchase costs - Travel and subsistence /€	Purchase costs - Equipment/€	Purchase costs - Other goods, works and services/€	Indirect costs/€	Total eligible costs	Maximum EU contribution to eligible costs
1	ITH	220.000,00	-	11.000,00	-	9.500,00	60.125,00	300.625,00	210.437,50
2	LINKS	278.100,00	10.000,00	11.000,00	22.000,00	-	77.775,00	398.875,00	398.875,00
3	ISQ	187.050,00	-	13.000,00	-	12.000,00	53.012,50	265.062,50	265.062,50
4	CBK	177.750,00	-	20.500,00	3.600,00	18.500,00	55.087,50	275.437,50	275.437,50
5	ENG	373.500,00	-	11.000,00	-	-	96.125,00	480.625,00	336.437,50
6	ROBOTTO	312.000,00	-	11.000,00	-	50.000,00	93.250,00	466.250,00	326.375,00
7	INESCTEC	190.000,00	-	14.000,00	-	76.000,00	70.000,00	350.000,00	350.000,00
8	HOLO	303.125,00	-	11.000,00	20.000,00	-	83.531,25	417.656,25	292.359,38
9	CINAMIL	188.000,00	-	20.500,00	-	-	52.125,00	260.625,00	260.625,00
10	ALPHA	285.600,00	34.000,00	11.000,00	-	-	74.150,00	404.750,00	283.325,00
	TOTALS	2.515.125,00	44.000,00	134.000,00	45.600,00	166.000,00	715.181,25	3.619.906,25	2.998.934,38

Table 5 – OVERWATCH budget

3. Project Management Processes

In order to reduce the risks involved in managing such a big and complicated project, the management of the OVERWATCH project necessitates the development of many management processes for reporting the project's progress, exchanging pertinent information, and quality assurance.

3.1. Management tools

To properly implement this PMP, a list of dedicated tools and methods are required. They have diverse objectives and rationale; however, they are fundamental supports in the overall project management. In the frame of the OVERWATCH project, they can be grouped in:

- ICT tools
- Tools for actions monitoring
- Tools for effort monitoring

3.1.1. ICT tools: Microsoft Teams (OVERWATCH Project)

In order to make sure the documentation exchange is properly organized and safe, an OVERWATCH Microsoft Team has been created and shared with all partners.

The Team comprises the following channels, available to the involved partners:

1. General
2. WP1
3. WP2
4. WP3
5. WP4
6. WP5
7. WP6

Microsoft Teams (Project OVERWATCH) serves as the Consortium's primary document store and collaboration hub. Electronic documents can be stored, searched for, tracked, and reported using this web-based collaborative platform (connected with Microsoft Office). The Consortium also makes use of Microsoft Teams' other essential features, including calling, video and online meetings, screen sharing, file sharing, and instant messaging. It is heavily utilized, in particular, for remote meetings and videoconferences, as an alternative to physical meetings. The only people who can access it are Consortium members.

All of the key documents and data pertinent to the OVERWATCH project are included in these tools, which the PC has generated. More specifically, they include at least:

- Contact information for the Consortium, along with roles from the WP to Task levels and for any pertinent activity or issue (e.g., communication or ethics and security). It is the duty of each partner to update this information;
- A "General" channel and a channel for each WP where all partners can access the pertinent documents. For each channel the following features are available:
 - a file repository which contains all the documentation that needs to be shared among the partners (i.e. recordings and minutes of the meetings, draft documents, presentations, templates, deliverables...). Updates to linked folders (such as the upload of pertinent files) will be handled by WP and Task Leaders;
 - a dedicated calendar, which keeps track of the meetings, deadlines and relevant events;

- a dedicated chat for quick messaging.
- Communication channel (WP5) where important materials for this activity are gathered. The key person in charge of this channel is the Communication and Dissemination Manager. It includes:
 - Project logo(s) and visual identity,
 - Communication pack, including for example brochures, infographics or videos,
 - Monitoring tools for communication and dissemination activities,
 - Press releases,
 - Templates for project documents (especially for deliverables).

As far as technical data (Earth Observation data, drones images, etc...) are concerned, the Consortium is going to adopt a dedicated tool, such as the open data repository Zenodo, for the storage and sharing of heavy data among partners.

3.1.2. Tools for actions monitoring

All major actions and future steps determined during meetings and contacts within the Consortium or with the PO are reported and tracked in an excel file named "OVERWATCH Action Log" that was created by the PC at the start of the project. This tool is essential to ensuring accurate project progress monitoring and deadline observance.

Each WP has its own sheet in the document and reports:

- Action number;
- Related task
- Action description;
- Responsible person(s);
- Other partners that support the action owner;
- Deadline for the action;
- Status of the action (open, in progress, done, cancelled, to be approved);
- Any relevant comment.

Once identified all this information, the tool automatically makes a recap (last status update) on the overall actions by status (i.e., number of open actions, of actions in progress and those done or cancelled). The continuous updating of the tasks under each task leader's control is their responsibility. They are informed well in advance of the regular meetings scheduled to track WP's advancements. The Action Log is examined during these meetings, and relevant updates by task are provided and discussed. An example (extract) for WP1 is provided here below.

Action Log		Status	#
OVERWATCH - WP1		Open	0
Last status update:		In Progress	1
06/04/2023		Done	14
		Cancelled	0
		Sum	15

No.	Task	Action Log description	Responsible	Support	Deadline	Status	Comments
1	WP1	Manage settings in WP1 weekly call // lack of chat functionality is a case when you log in via a link, that is then being opened in your default browser that has other TEAMS account logged in. In case of running two logged in TEAMS accounts in the same time, please copy link to another browser / open private tab / join directly from TEAMS app.	Emil Wrzosek	all	09/12/23	Done	Please copy meeting link to browser you are logged in with account connected to Overwatch Teams. For further support please contact: federico.monteforte@itacaweb.org ; admin@itacaweb.org
2	T1.1	Fill the EUB and AB tables	José Borges			Done	OVERWATCH_End Users and Advisory Boards.xlsx
3	T1.1	Provide (min) 5 references/partner for the SoTA table	José Borges			Done	OVERWATCH_SoTA.xlsx
4	T1.1	Provide comments on the methodology for capturing Use Cases and End-user requirements	José Borges			Done	Methodology.pptx
5	T1.1	Provide feedback on benefits and tasks for the OVERWATCH's Advisory and End-user boards	José Borges		09/12/22	Done	OVERWATCH_Advisory and End-user boards.docx
6	T1.1	Provide a draft version of presentation for mid-Jan Workshops	José Borges		16/12/22	Done	
7	T1.3	Establish a date for bi-weekly T1.3 meeting	José Borges		27/01/23	Done	https://doodle.com/meeting/participate/id/enR06Nie
8	T1.3	Discuss and freeze the microservice architecture pattern	Claudio Rossi	all	February 23	Done	
9	T1.3	Further detailing each architecture block	Claudio Rossi	all	February 23	Done	
10	T1.1	Contribute to D1.1 (draft)	José Borges	all	23/02/23	Done	Overwatch Deliverable_D1.1.docx
11	T1.1	Contribute to D1.1	José Borges	all	03/03/23	Done	Overwatch Deliverable_D1.1.docx
12	T1.1	Set a date and invite participants for AB meeting	José Borges	Emil Wrzosek	24/02/23	Done	
13	T1.1	D1.1 Ready for final revision + proofreading	José Borges	Emil Wrzosek	21/03/23	Done	
14	T1.1	Delivery of D1.1	José Borges	Emil Wrzosek	31/03/23	Done	
15	T1.3	D1.3 ToC drafted and shared	Giuseppe Veila		07/04/23	In Progress	

Figure 3: OVERWATCH Action Log – WP1 (Illustrative only)

3.2.1. Monthly overall coordination meetings

In order to facilitate the overall coordination of the project and make sure all partners are fully updated on the project activities, monthly plenary meetings are scheduled every second Friday of the month on the Microsoft Teams platform. All WP leaders are invited to report to all partners about the activities performed in their WP, the risks encountered and their remedy actions, and the next steps.

The minutes of the meetings, together with the recording, are provided in the MStTeams WP6 channel and clearly report the actions agreed upon and their responsible persons.

3.2.2. WP periodic meetings

Periodic online meetings are planned for each running WP, with a weekly or biweekly frequency according to the specific needs.

The WP leader is invited to chair the meeting and facilitate discussion among all partners involved in the WP on open issues and next steps. All decisions taken are reported in the meeting minutes stored, together with the recording, on the Teams channels.

3.2.3. Quarterly Progress meetings

Every three months, a Progress Meeting is scheduled with the PO, the project REVRs and the PC. In these meetings, the PC is asked to report on the project status, on the activities performed in the relative quarter, on the risks foreseen and on the future steps. Following the meeting, a Quarterly Progress Report is uploaded by the EUPr onto the portal as deliverable (see point 3.3.1.).

The preparation and execution of the Quarterly Progress Meetings with the PO follow a defined procedure that is now described in detail.

Procedure 1: Quarterly Progress Meetings with the PO

Responsible	Timeframe	Action
PO	- 1 month	Confirmation of the meeting date.
PC	- 3 weeks	Ask OVERWATCH WP Leaders for contributions to the meeting presentation regarding the status of each Work Package by sending the latest QPR.
PC	- 1 week	Send QPR draft to PO and REVRs.
PC, PO and REVRs	0	Quarterly Progress Meetings with PO and REVRs.
PC	+ 2 days	Send QPR draft with PO and REVRs' comments to all partners for review.
All partners	+ 1 week	Send comments and suggestions on the QPR draft to the PC.
PC	+ 10 days	Upload the final version of the QPR on the portal as deliverable.

3.3. Reporting

Every OVERWATCH beneficiary, including every consortium member, must adhere to a number of reporting guidelines. These techniques offer a useful means to evaluate the project's progress, yet the implementation of more sophisticated internal monitoring procedures is required to guarantee

the early identification of any deviation from the project plan and the application of the required corrective measures.

3.3.1. Quarterly Progress Reporting to the EUSPA

Every three months, a Quarterly Progress Report is provided to EUSPA and the Reviewers in order to inform them on the progress of the activities. The QPR consists of an excel file which includes the following information:

- Cover sheet: general information on the project (title, duration, partner list, ...)
- Objectives: description of project objectives as defined in the Description of Action
- Meetings: list of meetings that took place and the ones that are planned, with indication of location, dates and involved participants
- Project KPIs: data related to results of the project following the predefined KPIs types
- Deliverables: list of the deliverables and their status
- Quarters: summary of activities performed in the last quarter, their main open issues, risks and mitigating actions, and the next steps/opportunities

The QPR is uploaded in pdf format by the EUPr onto the portal as deliverable every three months. The preparation and delivery of the QPR follow a defined procedure, here described in details.

Procedure 2: Quarterly Progress Reporting to the PO

Responsible	Timeframe	Action
PC	- 1 month (to end of quarter)	Ask all OVERWATCH consortium partners for contributions to the quarterly report, regarding activities performed, spent PMs, Deliverables, Milestones and Risks.
All OVERWATCH consortium members	- 3 weeks	Send contributions to the QPR, regarding spent PMs, Deliverables, Milestones and Risks to the PC.
PC	- 2 weeks	Review all contributions from the OVERWATCH consortium members and submit the draft report to the PO and REVs.
PC, PO and REVs	- 10 days	Quarterly Progress Meeting
PC	- 1 week	Send QPR draft with PO and REVs' comments to all partners for review.
All partners	- 2 days	Send comments and suggestions on the QPR draft to the PC.
PC	0	Upload the final version of the QPR n the portal as deliverable.

3.4. Document repository

The repository of all the documentation necessary to the development of the project is the OVERWATCH Microsoft Teams. A back-up of all documentation is stored on the physical servers at the PC premises.

During the project life cycle, several technical documentation must be exchanged between the consortium members, which includes background technical documentation and project Deliverables..

3.4.1. Background Technical Documentation

Technical Background Information is all the information that is of critical relevance for the activities described in the OVERWATCG DoA to achieve the results established therein and in the GA. This

information must be shared within the project consortium in due time. The exchange of background technical documentation is made on the OVERWATCH Microsoft Teams in the relevant channel.

3.4.2. Deliverables

The OVERWATCH project foresees a rich list of Deliverables, defined in the GA and presented in section 2.3.2, representing the most relevant project’s technical results.

The Deliverables are results to be submitted to and evaluated by the EC, and a review process must occur before any Deliverable is accepted for submission to the portal.

The exchange of Deliverable documents or reports, in any stage of development, from draft to final version, is made on the OVERWATCH Microsoft Teams file repositories.

The Deliverable preparation, revision and submission procedure is described below:

Procedure 3: Deliverable submission

Responsible	Timeframe	Action
Phase 1 – Deliverable preparation		
DR	In due time	Discuss the contents of the Deliverable with the respective OVERWATCH WP Leader and Task Leaders. Ensure that all technical objectives and requisites of the document are in accordance with the established in the GA.
DR	In due time	Prepare a draft version of the Deliverable document and assign contributions to all involved partners; share the draft with the partners.
All involved partners	In due time	Provide contributions to the draft document to the DR
Phase 2 – Internal Review		
DR	- 4 weeks	Send the final draft to the identified internal reviewer(s).
Internal reviewer(s)	- 3 weeks	Review the Deliverable and provide comments and suggestionsto the DR for improvement.
DR	- 2 weeks	Send the final draft to the PC.
PC	- 1 week	Verify the quality of the Deliverable, in terms of form and structure and, in accordance with the established in the GA
Phase 3 – Submission to the portal		
EUPr	0	Upload the final version of the Deliverable document to the portal.
Phase 4 –Acceptance or request for changes		
PO and REVs	+3 weeks	Accept the Deliverable through the portal or request for further changes
EUPr	+3 weeks	Inform the DR of the outcome of the Deliverable review and: i) Confirm acceptance or ii) Forward the request for changes from the PO to the DR In the latter case, perform Phase 1 to 4 once again

3.4.3. Other Documents

Any technical information or documents that are not considered as background technical documentation or Deliverables, nor are considered as critical information, can be exchanged directly between the OVERWATCH partners without keeping track in the OVERWATCH Microsoft Team.